

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Molecular mechanisms that underlie penetrating activity in Crohn's Disease.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The Montreal B3 phenotype is defined by fistulizing, penetrating disease between loops of bowel or bowel and the skin; skin regions affected are frequently the perianal region. The exact fraction of CD IBD patients with B3 phenotype disease or B3-like disease is not known. Similarly, it is not completely understood whether penetrating disease can simply be accounted for by a more severe disease course, a secondary genetic contribution (separate from NOD2 but cooperating with IBD susceptibility genes to result in aggressive penetrating disease), or what is currently widely understood, an encompassed but discrete disease subtype or phenotype of Crohn's Disease.

Results

We measured total transcription in terminal ileum fibroblasts from patients with B3-phenotype Crohn's Disease for discovery and description of the molecular mechanisms that in total as a system contribute to and account for aggressive disease behavior of specific quality which results from alterations in cellular and organismal function. Penetrating activity is not widely believed to involve necrotizing microbial species.

1. A cell cycle phenotype in CD and the B3 phenotype: NLRP10 silencing.
 - a. Down regulation of NLRP10 can be thought of a compensatory change following NLRP10 activation during a prior cellular event or transcriptional encounter. We described a cellular sensor function of NLRP10 that posits this specific NLR gene is activated in response to large changes in cellular speed, or rate of cell cycle progression. A primary cell cycle phenotype resulting from a genetic or infectious insult that becomes latent or unresolved, or leads to deficits in responsiveness of the cell to diverse challenges, or leads to regenerative responses which can be altered may be a recurrent theme in the etiology of chronic disease.
 - b. Accordingly, we described CDK alterations as a defining component of humans with Parkinson's Disease, a pathology that remains to be etiologically seasoned despite identification of genetic susceptibility (variants in PARK2 or PINK1, and mutants of the alpha synuclein protein).
 - c. CDK5RAP3 was also a B3 phenotype component gene, and activated.
 - d. We previously found NLRP10 activation occurred concomitant with ATP8A2 and WIPI1 modulation following unrestricted cell cycling resulting from p53/Rb1 dKO in human embryonic stem cells. Consistent with a function for ATP8A2 in contexts where NLRP10 is activated or repressed, we found significant repression of ATP8A2 specific to the B3 phenotype.
2. Tp53inp1 activation.
 - a. The NLRP10 transcriptional feature was accompanied by activation of p53 target genes functioning in tumor suppression through, at least in part, cell cycle restriction.
3. PAX8 and Pax8-AS1 repression.
 - a. The data suggested a scenario involving attempted homeobox activation like which occurs during cancer cell genesis but without resulting in transformation.
 - b. PAX8 is a master homeobox regulator of transformation in human cells. The NLRP10 defect associated with a cellular stress or stimulus resulting in sensor activation attributed to a change in cycling speed or progression through mitosis was accompanied by induction of p53 target genes but failure to activate an oncogenic homeobox.
 - c. PAX8 silencing rather than induction, here, (separate from the magnitude of the change in the factor which also influences resultant cellular phenotype) might reflect partial recapitulation of a specific phase of tumor suppressor activation, cell cycle activity typically observed in transformed, transforming settings, or during "non-homeostatic" cell cycle behaviors (defects in exit from mitosis or significant changes in speed of cycling).
4. Cyb5a induction.
 - a. Cytochrome-related Nadph oxidase genetic variants found in humans with chronic granulomatous disease are among the few known genetic causes of disease phenotype featuring inflammatory-type penetration of the perianal region.
5. LRR15 and Igsf10 activation.
 - a. Ig-like receptors were activated in penetrating disease, from diverse gene families.
 - b. Other Ig-like and LRR-containing receptors were instead repressed or silenced in B3 subtype disease, including LRR8 family receptors with conventionally-restricted expression in T-cells
6. Ras pathway effectors and signaling.

- 1 7. TLR family signal transduction
- 2 a. TIRAP
- 3 b.
- 4 8. Growth factor signaling changes
- 5 a. Myeloid derived growth factor MYDGF was silenced.
- 6 b.
- 7 9. Major imprinting system alterations.
- 8 a. BAZ2A was activated.
- 9 10. Epigenetic changes in penetrating Crohn's Disease.
- 10 a.
- 11 11. LncRNAs of the B3 phenotype signature.
- 12 a. Lncrod was activated
- 13 b. Dancr was repressed
- 14 12. ARP2/3 functionality.
- 15 13. Nutrient sensing.
- 16 14. TCF21 activation.
- 17 a. TARID, a TCF21 antisense RNA, was also prominent in the penetrating phenotype gene signature.
- 18 15. Lymphocyte antigens at the membrane that influence recognition of self associated with tumor
- 19 surveillance and tolerogenic signaling.
- 20 a. Ly antigen expression in the hematopoietic compartment of humans with CD is significantly altered,
- 21 considering all phenotypes together.
- 22 b.
- 23 16. Exhaustion
- 24 17. Senescence
- 25 18. Cytolytic functions
- 26 19. Epithelial and structural systems that provide barrier defense and architectural support that is,
- 27 broadly speaking, compromised in penetrating disease.
- 28 a. Keratins involved included
- a. SPINT
20. Major changes in genomic integration events.
- a. INTS
- b. Nbpf
21. B3-specific cytokines and chemokines.
22. Kinase signaling in the B3 phenotype.
- a. Map
- b. The kinase expression alterations may reflect differences in growth factor signaling or energetic
- functions of the AKT, mTOR, and PI3K pathways.
23. Perturbed complement pathway function.
24. Cell polarity is altered in penetrating disease.
- a. BBS9
- b.
25. Lysosomal biogenesis machinery.
- a. Hps
26. Nuclear transport pathways are altered in the B3 phenotype
- a. A NPC structural component, nucleoporin Nup43, was repressed.
- b. Phax, an adaptor-type molecule for RNA export from the nucleus was also silenced.
27. Cell death program in the B3 phenotype of Crohn's Disease.
28. Steroid metabolism
- a. SCD5
29. Cholesterol and oxysterol signaling in B3 subtype disease in humans with CD.

- 1 30. Molecules that function in axon guidance and similar processes
- 2 a. RGMB silencing
- 3 b. RGMA was instead activated.
- 4 31. Wound healing and regenerative responses
- 5 a. NNT
- 6 b. CTHRC1
- 7 32. Nucleotide biosynthetic pathways
- 8 a. APRT
- 9 b. HPRT
- 10 c. MGMT silencing
- 11 33. Mitosis-related programs.
- 12 a. AMN repression
- 13 b.
- 14 34. Neuroactive machinery and signals
- 15 a. BDNF repression
- 16 b.
- 17 35. DNA damage and repair
- 18 a. MSH5, a mismatch repair enzyme.
- 19 b. BRSK2
- 20 c. Fanconi anemia pathway molecules:
- 21 36. Physiologically oriented hormones and neuropeptides
- 22 a.
- 23 37. Molecules associated with neurodegenerative disease
- 24 a. APP activation
- 25 b. Alpha synuclein
- 26 38. Isomerase chemistry functionality changes
- 27 39. Major nuclear factors
- 28 a. RXRA activation.
40. Vps secretory pathway changes: indication of relation to changes in utilization of energy in the cell or nutrient (amino acid) sensing pathways
- a. Vps37b
- b. Vps36
41. NLR family genes are specifically perturbed in the B3 phenotype of CD.
- a. NLRP1 activation was observed, together with NLRP10 silencing.
- b. NLRP5 was also significantly induced in the penetrating subtype, which could be of relevance to lymphocyte antigen immunological synapse interactions or to speculated dysfunction in cytolytic or oxidizing immune cell function that might contribute to fistulizing disease.
42. TLR family genes in the B3 phenotype.
- a. Flagellin sensor TLR5 was activated.
43. Cyclooxygenases, eicosanoids and leukotrienes of the B3 program
44. Metabolic pathways in the B3 phenotype
45. Oxidative-reduction machinery alterations in penetrating disease in CD.
- a. Txnip was activated.
46. Small nucleolar RNAs
47. Vesicular trafficking and secretory pathway
48. Deamination-based nuclear processes
- a. CDA silencing
- b. ADA silencing
- c. ADARB silencing o
49. Golgi apparatus alteration.

- 1 50. Purinergic receptors
- 2 51. Peroxisome composition
- 3 52. ATP-synthetic and mitochondrial functions
- 4 53. Aging, rejuvenation associated and related
- 5 a. Mboat1 activation
- 6 b. Paqr_
- 7 54. Junctional composition
- 8 a.
- 9 55. Ion channels
- 10 a. CLIC2
- 11 56. ATP-binding cassette expression changes in the B3 subtype.
- 12 57. Ubiquitin
- 13 58. Proteasome
- 14 59. Ribosome
- 15 60. DNA replication and transcription
- 16 a. POLI activation
- 17 61. Other nuclear processes associated with transformation.
- 18 a. SLIRP
- 19 62. RNA chemistry functionality changes.
- 20 a. PAN2 ribonuclease activation
- 21 b.
- 22 63. Activation of MILR1, a mast cell receptor.
- 23 64. Serine peptidase expression.
- 24 65. Collagens and enzymes that use collagen as substrate
- 25 a.
- 26 66. Glycoproteins in the B3 subtype plasma membrane and subtype organelles.
- 27 67. SH3-receptor signaling
- 28 68. Cysteine-rich gene products altered in penetrating Crohn's Disease.
69. Cell adhesion.
70. Immune receptor expression profile in penetrating disease (cluster of differentiation)
71. Immune receptors of diverse gene family origin
- a.
72. Other components of the penetrating Crohn's Disease-specific signature
- a. Gusbp11
- b. Crybg crystalline family
73. PIANP receptor activation.
74. Cytokine signaling intermediaries.
75. Splicing machinery.
76. Heme and iron transport and metabolism.
77. Platelet-specific genes and clotting machinery.
78. Nucleic acid signaling.
79. Cilia and flagellar cellular processes in penetrating disease.
80. B3-phenotype microRNAs.
81. Carbonyl reductase machinery.
82. Glycolytic metabolic pathways.
83. Nuclear factors
84. Phospholipase signaling
85. Wnt signaling and TLE factors that function in TCF/Lef signaling.
86. Anti-microbial effectors
87. Translation machinery.

- 1 88. Tumor suppression related
- 2 a. TEF silencing
- 3 89. WAS complex associated.
- 4 90. Other soluble immune effectors
- 5 a. MIF silencing
- 6 91. Chemotactic functional changes separate from chemokine modulation and guidance cue alteration.
- 7 92. Transient receptor potential channels and machinery used for mechanosensation and proprioception.
- 8 a. Trp channels were a central feature of NLRP10 activation signature in hES cells following deletion of p53/Rb, which occurred together with modulation of ATP8A2, nutrient sensor machinery including Tsc/TBD family genes, TNF superfamily effectors as well as phosphoinositide-based WIPI family molecules.
- 9 93. MGMT and purine biosynthesis.
- 10 a. Other MGMT or purine/pyrimidine metabolic pathway changes:
 - 11 i. _____
- 12 94. Cyclic nucleotide and nucleic acid signaling is defective and a major component of the penetrating subtype gene signature in Crohn's Disease.
- 13 a. Mavs induction was observed
- 14 b. Ifih1 (MDA5)
- 15 c. cGAS: _____
- 16 d. Tlr2, Tlr3 and Tlr7
- 17 e. Rig-I (DDX58) and LGP2 (Dhx58)
- 18 f. AIM2
- 19 g. Prkra
- 20 h. ADAR changes can be included here if desired rather than deamination.
 - 21 i. Deamination-based self non self innate response was suggested in the literature
- 22 i. Sting silencing was described here separately.
- 23 j. Oas family gene expression
 - 24 i. Oas activation ligand description:
- 25 k. Other
- 26 l. Other cyclic nucleotide genes:
 - 27 i. Cant1
 - 28 ii. Cnbp family
- 29 95. S1PR receptors
- 30 a. S1pr3 and to a lesser extent, S1pr2
- 31 b. S1PR5 was silenced.
- 32 96. Ceramide biosynthesis
- 33 a. CERS5 silencing
- 34 b. Galc induction
- 35 c. Cptp deficiency
- 36 d. Gba2 activation.
- 37 97. DCXR and CBR3 silencing.
- 38 a. Modest Cbr4 activation was observed
- 39 b. Carbonyl reductase function was suggested to be relevant to pathogenesis of penetrating disease.
- 40 98. Keratins 18, 19, 33b, 34 and 10 are silenced in
- 41 a. Krtap1-5 and 1-1 were also silenced

- 1 99. Collagen type molecule changes
- 2 a. PLOD1 and PLOD2 were silenced.
- 3 b. LOC107985728, was activated.
- 4 c.
- 5 100. Global NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit A1 complex silencing
- 6 a. These included a suite of Nduf genes, including Ndufa1
- 7 b. Other Nduf genes included
- 8 101. EMT in penetrating Crohn's.
- 9 a. Zeb2 activation specific to B3 subtype
- 10 b. This is a separate finding from the recent discovery of EMT as a relevant component process in
- 11 cells containing NOD2 mutation
- 12 c. This is also separate from the finding that cells from humans with CD possess significant EMT
- 13 program alterations, without regard to subtype
- 14 102. Spondin activation is specifically dysregulated in penetrating Crohn's Disease.
- 15 103. Tomm5 and timm8 silencing.
- 16 104. Mfsd mobilization in the penetrating Crohn's phenotype.
- 17 a. This included MFSD9 activation.
- 18 105. Cdk18 silencing in the B3 phenotype.
- 19 a. INKA, a CDK associated lncRNA was a component gene of the B3 phenotype.
- 20 106. Spint2 silencing.
- 21 a. Kik family genes:
- 22 107. GAL, a galanin and GMAP prepropeptide is silenced.
- 23 108. PVR silencing.
- 24 a. Pvrig was activated.
- 25 109. Transposase activation in penetrating disease.
- 26 a. This included POGZ and PGBD5
- 27 110. Ubr7 ligase activation
- 28 111. Ube4e
112. HMB5 metabolic deficiency.
113. Dhfr family genes.
114. Nuclear transport
115. Tbc1d6, tbc1d5, tbc1d3d, and tbc1d15 are activated in the B3 phenotype.
116. Sphingomyelin phosphodiesterase repression.
117. Tcim, an immune regulator, is activated.
118. Clathrin light and heavy chain silencing: CTHA and CTHB.
119. L3MBT3L activation in penetrating Crohn's Disease.
120. Purine and pyrimidine nucleotide metabolism alterations central to the penetrating subtype of Crohn's Disease.
- a. MGMT was silenced.
- b. MPG was silenced.
- c. TPMT was silenced.

121. Dermatan sulfate epimerase, DSE, is silenced in penetrating Crohn's Disease.
122. Purinergic signaling activation.
 - a. This included P2R
123. Peraxin activation in B3 subtype.
124. BTN3A3 and Btn3a1 activation.
 - a. Parp9 enzyme was also modulated in the B3 subtype
125. Lamc2 and phospholamman modulation.
126. Ubl5 silencing.
127. Malt1 silencing.
128. Card11 in penetrating disease.
129. Il18bp and IL-16 activation in the B3 subtype.
130. Anoctamin activation.
 - a. This included ANO4.
131. Snhg repression.
132. Isomerases
 - a. PIN1
 - b. PPIA
133. Amine oxidase machinery modulation in penetrating disease.
 - a. AOC3 induction.
134. VIPR2 activation.
135. Notch1 and Bace2 activation in penetrating IBD.
136. Elaine, a neutrophil elastase is modestly but significantly activated in B3 phenotype.
137. Coenzyme related changes in the B3 phenotype.
 - a. Coq8a was activated.
 - b. Ubiquinol related molecules were also modulated: UQCRQ/B and UQCR
138. TSR3 silencing indicates ribosomal changes in penetrating disease.
139. Sarcoglycan in B3 subtype.
 - a. SGCA silencing.
140. Reticulon silencing in B3 CD.
141. Clic6 and CLIC2 activation in penetrating Crohn's.
142. Parkin activation in penetrating Crohn's.
143. Timp1 silencing.
144. Suprabasin silencing.
145. Uba7 activation in B3 Crohn's.
 - a. Connect to CRL and cullin/NEDD.
146. Erythrodrodrone activation.
147. ARSD and SULF2 activation.
148. Mvb genes.
 - a. Pofut
 - b. UAP- associated
 - c. Kdelr related
 - d. Tv-related
 - e. Golgi associated
 - f. UPR and related
149. Sperm tissue expression in the B3 phenotype.
 - a. Odf 11 and a related gene were active
 - b. Spata genes spata6 and Spata13 were induced.
 - c. Spaca6 activation was observed

- 1 150. Lyve1 and SELPLG silencing.
- 2 151. Ubxn2b and Ubxn11 activation
- 3 152. Succinate receptor and SDH enzyme changes.
- 4 153. HAAO activation.
- 5 154. Plasminogen activation alteration.
- 6 155. Gliomedin and metrn silencing.
- 7 156. Glucokinase induction.
- 8 157. Interferon gamma receptor activation.
- 9 158. Trank1 activation.
- 10 159. Mlst8 deficiency in penetrating Crohn's.
- 11 a. Elapor family silencing was observed.
- 12 160. Phospholipase PINLYP activation. .
- 13 161. NPIPA1/2/3 activation indicates transcriptional transgression.
- 14 162. Ataxin family genes.
- 15 163. Lyst deficiency concomitant with TRAF3 induction.
- 16 164. Nsf silencing.
- 17 165. Periostin silencing.
- 18 166. Angpt4 activation.
- 19 167. Follistatin deficiency.
- 20 168. SST activation.
- 21 169. RIPK4 deficiency.
- 22 170. FAH deficiency.
- 23 171. Trim22 activation.
- 24 172. Hexd activation.
- 25 173. Cortexin and ARC silencing.
- 26 174. Alox12 activation.
- 27 175. Tcf15 deficiency.
- 28 176. Oscar silencing.
177. Ran silencing.
178. Ces1 silencing
179. TIA1 activation.
180. Polyamine synthesis deficiency.
181. Tlcd5 and Tlcd2 activation.
182. Kiaa0408 activation.
183. Gas6 silencing
184. C2orf27A activation
185. Cyt11 induction, a chemokine type molecule.
186. LOC101927999 activation.
187. LOC101929756 silencing.
188. Myomesin and asporin deficiency.
189. Aggrecan silencing.
190. LOC101929756
191. Nr2c1 and Nr4a1 induction.
192. Nfkbid, nfkia, and nfkb1 activation.
193. Chst7 and chst1w deficient.
194. LOC112268301 activation.
195. Mevalonate signaling.